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Structural changes in the export-import turnover of the Russian Federation under sanctions

KEYWORDS

export,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of structural changes in Russia's export-import turnover under sanctions is driven by the necessity to ensure economic stability, diversify trading partners, mitigate external risks, adapt to the new conditions of the global economy, and strengthen the country's strategic autonomy. These measures enable Russia to adapt to restrictive measures, develop domestic production, and establish new logistics chains, thereby enhancing the economy's resilience and long-term development.

The study is aimed at conducting an analysis of changes in the foreign trade export-import turnover of the Russian Federation under sanctions.

Materials and methods. The research utilized statistical data from Rosstat (Russian Federal State Statistics Service) and international organizations, as well as scientific articles and analytical materials from peer-reviewed journals. Research methods included statistical analysis of export and import dynamics before and after the imposition of sanctions, comparative analysis across industries and partner countries, and SWOT analysis to assess the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the sanctions.

Results. The paper presents an empirical generalization and analysis of structural shifts in Russia's foreign trade system caused by unprecedented sanctions restrictions imposed by Western countries. It substantiates the primary causes and directions of the diversification of Russian export commodity flows and energy exports, the specifics of forming a new export geography amid the differentiation of partner countries, and the restructuring of the entire logistics of global commodity distribution cooperation.

Conclusion. Russia has successfully adapted to the sanctions and import contraction by diversifying fuel supplies to Asia and the Middle East. The sanctions have led to the degradation of trade and economic relations with unfriendly countries and a strengthening of cooperation with Asia, which has increased trade dependence on China, India, and Turkey, thereby elevating foreign trade risks. The development of ties with neutral countries is hampered by logistical challenges and the threats of secondary sanctions. Under pressure from the West, Russia must develop international cooperation through the participation of business structures in global and regional formats, while continuing its policy of openness and support for Russian projects abroad.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this topic stems from the fact that sanctions significantly impact a country's foreign economic activity, inducing shifts in the structure of its exports and imports. Understanding these structural transformations enables the development of more targeted state support measures, stimulates the growth of priority industries, and mitigates the adverse effects of restrictive measures. Analyzing changes in the economic structure facilitates more accurate forecasting of the development of foreign economic activity and strategic planning for the future.

Since February 2022, Russia has been under virtually unprecedented pressure from the West. The volume of sanctions and foreign trade restrictions imposed by Western nations targeting individuals, companies, and the transport sector of the Russian Federation significantly exceeds similar measures previously enacted against Iran, Syria, and North Korea. Certain foreign markets have become entirely inaccessible to Russian suppliers, substantially complicating the maintenance of economic growth rates for an economy deeply integrated into the system of globally distributed production.

Amid the escalation of anti-Russian sanctions by the EU countries, G7 nations, the USA, and their allies, the Russian Federation has altered the format, structure, and geography of its international cooperation. The country's system of foreign economic ties, integrated into the global economic system, has encountered a sharp increase in fragmentation under sanctions, affecting economic, financial, technological, resource-commodity, military-political, information-network, educational, and other spheres of international collaboration.

The risks of a growing imbalance in the international financial system (exemplified by the freezing of the Russian Federation's international financial reserves and the exclusion of its systemically important banks from the SWIFT interbank messaging system for cross-border payments) have precipitated a crisis in global governance institutions. A significant rise in uncertainty within the global economy and politics has led to a comprehensive systemic transformation of globalization processes and intensified the fragmentation of world trade.

The study is aimed at conducting an analysis of changes in the foreign trade export-import turnover of the Russian Federation under sanctions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials comprised statistical data from the Federal Customs Service of Russia, Rosstat (Russian Federal State Statistics Service), and International Organizations. Additionally, scientific articles and analytical materials published in peer-reviewed periodicals were utilized, including: Eastern Economic Journal; Studies on Russian Economic Development; Regional Research of Russia; Steel in Translation; RUDN Journal of Economics; Scientific Reports; Geography and Natural Resources; Economics and Entrepreneurship, among others.

The research methods included statistical analysis (examining export and import dynamics before and after the imposition of sanctions), comparative analysis (evaluating changes by industry and partner countries), and SWOT analysis (assessing strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with sanctions).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Under sanctions, Russia has reduced its energy exports and increased agricultural exports, while imports of technological products have declined. Domestic production and import substitution have intensified, particularly in machinery and electronics, thereby reducing dependence on Western markets.

M. Bali et al. examine the indirect impact of sanctions on non-prohibited exports to Russia using a gravity model of trade that incorporates a time-varying sanctions index. The researchers found that sanctions led to a reduction in exports of non-prohibited goods from some European countries and an increase in such exports from others [1].

A. M. Kalinin addresses issues related to assessing import dependency and the outcomes of import substitution policy during the period 2016–2020. The researcher established that for the vast majority of industries and product types, no monotonic decrease in import dependency was observed between 2016 and 2020. In the author's view, the currently declared emphasis on ensuring technological sovereignty can be considered justified; however, the practical implementation of import substitution policy compared to the 2016–2020 period must be more effective both in terms of scale and the efficiency of the instruments applied [2].

M. Y. Malkina analyzes the rates and factors of industrial growth in Russian regions during the period of the Special Military Operation and the imposition of new anti-Russian sanctions in 2022–2023. The author revealed that interregional differences

in industrial growth rates and those of its main sectors were significant both during the stagnation period (2022) and the period of moderate growth (2023). Over the two years, industrial growth rates ranged from -26.8% in the Kaliningrad Region to +38.3% in the Bryansk Region. The scholar identified a statistically significant positive influence of human capital quality, as well as the share of the communications and telecommunications sector in the gross regional product, on industrial growth in Russian regions in both 2022 and 2023. The researcher also identified a negative influence on this growth from the level of economic openness, expressed as dependency on imports, exports, and foreign investments [3].

D. M. Tavrikov and N. N. Yashalova examine the foreign economic activity of the Russian metal products industry with a focus on exports. The authors proposed and justified measures to stimulate exports of metal products and ensure their competitiveness on global markets, including the abolition of export duties, compensation for export logistics costs, reimbursement of certification and homologation costs in friendly countries, the creation of financial mechanisms and instruments to ensure stable trade, and subsidizing logistics for rail and container transportation within Russia [4].

In another study, D. M. Tavrikov and N. N. Yashalova review the main types of sanctions and assess their impact on the operations of domestic metal products companies. The scholars conducted an analysis of the dynamics of export-import operations and average prices for metal products industry output for 2021–2023 [5].

A. R. Stephens and J. W. Yoo demonstrate that Russia has undergone significant changes in its export specialization, which likely indicate deindustrialization in sectors such as locomotive and aircraft manufacturing. The scholars have found that Russian primary commodities, including mineral fuels, non-fuel minerals (e.g., nickel), and fertilizers, currently remain a strong advantage [6].

V. Naumov and E. Zhiryaeva assess the risks of economic modernization caused by technological sanctions. The authors suggest that the imposed sanctions have had a minor impact on the actual import of computer hardware components into Russia. Today, the main exporters are China, Taiwan, Vietnam, and Malaysia. For countries without export controls, the growth of imports to Russia over 15 years was an order of magnitude greater for both processors (160%) and integrated circuits (224%) compared to countries with export controls [7].

S. R. Milyakin et al. analyze the supply of automobiles to the domestic market across key segments, both historically and currently. They identify four main

segments: production of domestic brands, localized production of foreign brands, import of new vehicles, and import of used vehicles. The researchers note that a shortage in the low-price segment will create opportunities for domestic brand production, while in the mid-price segment, opportunities will arise for the gradual localization of Chinese brands [8].

S. V. Golovanova and E. V. Krekhovets provide a quantitative assessment of the potential medium-term demand of the Russian economy for plastics and plastic products under the imposed sanctions. The scholars indicate significant unmet needs for import substitution in plastics, which cannot be satisfied solely through the expansion of domestic production capacity [9].

N. V. Galtseva notes that sanctions have altered the operating conditions for Russia's gold mining industry. The author examines factors complicating the industry's operations and leading to increased production costs and decreased gold selling prices: a ban on foreign trade operations for the largest partner banks of subsoil users, embargoes by foreign states on purchasing Russian gold, and restrictions on importing foreign equipment and spare parts, as well as the reduction of the US dollar to ruble exchange rate by the Central Bank of Russia from May 2022 to January 2023 [10].

C. M. Acosta writes that banned Russian timber is still being imported into the EU despite sanctions aimed at limiting revenue from timber sales. An international consortium of investigative journalists has identified new routes through China, Turkey, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan to track cases of circumventing bans and supplying Russian timber to the EU, noting an increase in EU timber imports from several countries following the imposition of sanctions against Russia [11].

L. Sitdikova studies the impact of sanctions on the development of Russian agriculture. According to the author's data, overall agricultural production in the Russian agro-industrial complex has grown by 33.2%, and food production – by 43%. Thus, the agricultural sector demonstrates an ability to adapt to new conditions, recover quickly from external shocks, and enhance its production and economic potential [12].

A. G. Ibragimov et al. analyze the state of Russia's food security under international sanctions. The authors establish that Russia's agrarian policy, aimed at supporting agricultural producers and import substitution, has yielded positive results over the past decade. Food products are categorized into three groups based on self-sufficiency levels: export-oriented (grain, fish, vegetable oils), insufficiently supplied

(milk, potatoes, vegetables, fruits), and sufficiently supplied (meat and eggs). According to the scholars, export-oriented industries are the most efficient and fastest-growing. The authors propose a set of recommendations for improving the market situation under international sanctions: (a) for the external market – measures to reorient export channels and establish new supply chains; (b) for the domestic market – a program for the preferential purchase of domestically produced food for low-income residents [13].

In the Russian energy sector, sanctions have led to a decline in oil and gas exports, particularly to Western countries. Domestic consumption has increased, while supplies to alternative markets have expanded. Imports of equipment and technologies for the energy sector have decreased, stimulating the development of domestic solutions.

A. Rajayya et al. note that Russia and Ukraine are important suppliers of raw materials, including metals, fertilizers, and neon gas for semiconductors, which are widely used in global manufacturing. Countries such as Brazil, India, and others have increased their export volumes to compensate for the trade deficit created by Russia and Ukraine. The scholars analyze how trade diversion has helped developed, developing, and transition economies cope with the consequences of the conflict in their export and import flows within global merchandise trade [14].

H. Huang et al. note that the Russo-Ukrainian conflict that erupted in 2022 exacerbated the natural gas shortage in European countries. The scholars constructed a model for the propagation of the coal supply crisis under the Russo-Ukrainian conflict using a cascading failure model [15].

M. Li et al. show that sanctions targeting the energy sector are primary drivers of volatility in oil prices and the stock prices of energy companies. Both direct and indirect sanctions demonstrate comparable spillover effects on oil and stock prices. Direct sanctions have greater explanatory power for stock price fluctuations, while indirect sanctions have greater explanatory power for oil price fluctuations [16].

J. Gars et al. assess who “wins” and “loses” more from the reduction in Russian oil exports. According to the authors’ calculations, a 10% reduction in exports would result in losses for Russian producers of USD 290 million per day, equivalent to 5% of GDP, primarily due to lower domestic prices. Russian consumers would benefit from export restrictions by gaining access to cheaper oil if Russia were to cut exports [17].

A. Tavadyan examines the impact of the 2022 Western sanctions against Russia on the restructuring of the global oil trade. According to the author’s estimates, by

2023, 38.6% of Russian oil exports had been redirected through India, accompanied by significant price anomalies. This phenomenon led to a substantial revision of GDP growth rates both in Russia and in oil-importing countries [18].

A. V. Fedotova emphasizes that the tightening of sanctions and the embargo on supplies of Russian oil and petroleum products have stimulated interest in parallel (or gray) imports, which began to play a significant role in Russia's foreign economic policy and its economy as a whole. The author analyzes the impact of parallel imports on the Russian economy, identifies the strengths and weaknesses of this policy, and proposes measures corresponding to the current economic situation [19].

M. A. Makushin examines the impact of the ban on Russian coal imports by European Union countries. According to the author, the import ban will have practically no effect on the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia), the Sakhalin Region, the Khabarovsk Territory, and the Trans-Baikal Territory. The most significant reduction in supplies to Europe will affect extensive holdings in the Kemerovo and Novosibirsk regions, as well as the Republic of Khakassia. It has been established that smaller companies will suffer more in terms of shares, as EU countries account for more than 50% of their export supplies [20].

Under sanctions, Russia's trade turnover with Western countries declined, while it increased with Asian countries and other alternative partners. Russia intensified its foreign trade with new markets to compensate for the restrictions.

V. A. Skvortsova et al. found that the intensification of Russia's trade with BRICS nations in both imports and exports opens new horizons for the Russian economy. Economic modernization requires Russia to actively seek new partnerships and memberships in international associations such as BRICS, as well as to engage in expanded dialogue with Latin America, Africa, and Asia [21].

N. A. Budarina writes that the SCO countries represent a significant market for the export of Russian goods and services. The author demonstrates that Russia has begun actively developing domestic production, i.e., implementing import substitution for foreign products, including through cooperation with member countries of the Organization [22].

V. V. Glinskii et al. consider the prospects for increasing exports of Russian products to Africa, which would allow for the formation of a strategy for working with a portfolio of industries and goods in foreign markets [23].

V. Dodonov investigates the impact of the situation following the West's imposition of anti-Russian sanctions in 2022 on the foreign trade of CIS countries. The author

concludes that some CIS economies increased their transit potential in trade between the Russian Federation and Western countries in 2022–2024, including through re-export [24].

Yu. Shokamanov et al. analyze the impact of anti-Russian sanctions on trade and economic relations between Kazakhstan and Russia. According to the researchers, imports from Russia decreased due to restrictions on the supply of certain goods and the withdrawal of a number of companies from the Russian market. Kazakhstan increased its exports to Russia by almost a quarter, mainly through supplies of machinery, equipment, and chemical products. At the same time, risks have increased for Kazakhstan regarding the imposition of secondary sanctions on Kazakh producers and foreign financial institutions re-exporting sanctioned goods, dual-use goods, and “high-priority” goods to Russia [25].

Denis Gonchar, Director of the Fourth Department of CIS Countries at the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, stated in an interview with TASS that Russian-Armenian trade turnover in January–May 2023 increased by 86% compared to the same period last year, and Armenian exports to Russia increased by a record 3.3 times. He also emphasized that Armenia is one of the main beneficiaries of EAEU membership [26].

A. Golubkin et al. assess the impact of European Union economic sanctions on the volume and structure of trade between Russia and Croatia in 2022–2024. The authors' results indicate a significant reduction in volume and a change in the structure of mutual trade between the Russian Federation and Croatia under numerous trade restrictions from the European Union. Economic sanctions had a greater impact on the exchange of goods between the countries in the engineering sector and chemical industry products [27].

Thus, a number of researchers examining the impact of sanctions on the parameters of Russia's international economic cooperation in the 2022/2023 period point to the blocking of large-scale trade and economic ties with the EU, the USA, and their closest allies, such as Canada, Australia, Japan, and South Korea. The analysis shows that the latter have essentially lost their role as partners of the Russian Federation in all areas of international cooperation. Meanwhile, amid the transformation of the global order's architecture and the development of a bipolar world order, there is a systematic increase in the role of both individual countries – India, Turkey, and China – and the BRICS association participants in strengthening and expanding foreign economic ties with Russia on the platform of a new strategic format of international cooperation. Furthermore, Russia is actively expanding cooperation with countries

of the Middle East, Asia, and Africa, signifying a strengthening of the southern vector of trade and economic integration and cooperation.

The analyzed studies show that under sanctions, Russia has intensified trade with BRICS countries, Asia, Latin America, and Africa, developing import substitution and new markets. CIS countries and Kazakhstan are strengthening trade with Russia despite sanctions, and Armenia has significantly increased its exports to Russia. Overall, countries are adapting their trade strategies, seeking new partnerships and markets to overcome restrictions and sanctions.

RESULTS

At the beginning of 2022 (prior to the imposition of sanctions), the Russian Federation directed over 55% of its export volumes to EU countries, Japan, South Korea, Canada, and the USA within the framework of its international cooperation. However, by the end of 2022, this share had decreased to 40% [28] (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Structural changes in the foreign trade export-import turnover of the Russian Federation, million USD

The Russian Federation has significantly strengthened international cooperation with countries of the Asia-Pacific region and has successfully reoriented the geography of its export-import supply chains.

The analysis revealed that Russia's export-import trade volumes with EU countries decreased by 31.38% (USD 72,819 million). Meanwhile, export-import trade volumes with Asia-Pacific countries increased by 17.88% (USD 57,149 million). Export-import trade volumes with CIS countries increased by 34.22% (USD 23,051 million), and with countries of the Middle East, Asia, Africa, and Latin America, they increased by 25.18% (USD 45,119 million).

The crisis in Ukraine has triggered global structural changes in the transportation channels for commodity flows from the Russian Federation, a significant portion of which have been redirected towards the Asian region. Russia has strengthened and is now actively developing international cooperation with the People's Republic of China and the Republic of India.

Thus, by the end of 2022, Russia-China trade turnover increased by 43.4%, reaching USD 190.27 billion, and by the end of 2023, it increased by 26.31%, reaching USD 240.11 billion [29].

Russia-India trade turnover by the end of 2022 increased by 220%, reaching USD 32.5 billion, and by the end of 2023, it increased by 100%, amounting to USD 65 billion [30].

It is also necessary to note the role of developing international relations with the Republic of Türkiye. By the end of 2022, Russia-Türkiye trade turnover increased by 86%, reaching USD 62 billion, and by the end of 2023, it stabilized at USD 56 billion [31]. It is important to note the fact that supplies of sanctioned Russian goods to EU countries are actively developing through Türkiye. However, in 2023, threats of secondary sanctions being imposed on Turkish companies acting as intermediaries increased.

Nevertheless, the total trade turnover of the Russian Federation with Türkiye, China, and India, amounting to USD 684.77 billion by the end of 2022, already exceeded the total trade turnover with EU countries (USD 259.22 billion) by 164% (USD 425.55 billion). This indicates the significant efforts of the Russian Federation's leadership in the field of international relations to adapt the export sector of the economy to sanctions restrictions across almost all areas of foreign trade cooperation.

An analysis of fundamental structural changes in the foreign trade turnover of the Russian Far East most clearly demonstrates the global shift in the structure of the Russian Federation's international relations [32] (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Structural changes in the foreign trade turnover of the Far East, million USD

Analyzing the structural changes in the foreign trade turnover of the Far East for the period 2017/2022, broken down by the presented organizations and associations, a significant increase in the share of foreign trade turnover with APEC countries by USD 16,332 million in monetary terms (+127%) should be noted. Equally significant is the substantial increase in the share of foreign trade turnover with EAEU countries by USD 1,144 million (+783%), with CIS countries – by USD 670 million (+446%), and with other countries – by USD 3,790 million (+338%).

Furthermore, due to the rupture of trade relations between the Russian Federation and OECD countries and EU countries, the Far East experienced a sharp decline in the share of foreign trade turnover by USD 5,613 million (-52%) and USD 1,246 million (-64%), respectively.

Foreign economic policy has seen a strengthened emphasis on bilateral and multilateral cooperation with developing countries, which represent the most dynamic part of the global economy and enhance the resilience of the Russian economy under conditions of uncertainty.

Thus, due to the impact of sanctions from the EU, the US, and their allies – including the ban on importing Russian oil via maritime routes, the ban on cargo insurance, and the introduction of a price cap on crude oil set at USD 60 per barrel – the Russian

fuel and energy complex (FEC) sharply reduced oil production volumes. Under the current sanctions regime, international cooperation in implementing new oil and gas production projects in Russia has been disrupted, with sanctions affecting the supply of foreign technologies and modern equipment [33] (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3 Dynamics of crude oil exports from Russia in 2018-2023, million tons

Based on the analysis, an overall reduction in crude oil export volumes by 13.6 million tons (-5.2%) was noted during the studied period. As a result of the sanctions impact in the 2022/2023 period, exported volumes of crude oil to EU countries decreased by 55.2 million tons (-45.09%) compared to 2021. Meanwhile, exported volumes of crude oil from Russia to Asia-Pacific (APR) countries increased by 55.1 million tons (+79.5%), and exported volumes to other countries increased by 15.01 million tons (+38.19%).

The responsive countermeasures of the Russian Federation, serving as one of the methods of effective state management of economic processes under global sanctions pressure, are associated with the development of international economic

cooperation. This is implemented through a ban on selling oil under contracts based on the mechanism of setting a price cap for oil, which essentially compels Russian oil producers to develop alternative sales channels.

The sabotage (explosions) of the Nord Stream 1 and Nord Stream 2 gas pipelines served as the primary reason for the reduction in supplies of Russian gas to the European Union countries [34] (see Fig. 4).

Figure 4 Dynamics of pipeline gas exports from Russia, billion cubic meters

The analysis reveals an overall reduction in pipeline gas export volumes by 119 billion cubic meters (-54.09%) between 2018 and 2023. As a result of the sabotage on the Nord Stream 1 and Nord Stream 2 gas pipelines during the 2022/2023 period, exported volumes of pipeline gas to EU countries decreased by 130 billion cubic meters (-83.87%) compared to 2021. Meanwhile, exported volumes of pipeline gas from Russia to Asia-Pacific (APR) countries increased by 14.61 billion cubic meters (+140.61%), and exported volumes to other countries increased by 9.4 billion cubic meters (+21.07%).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, the Russian Federation has demonstrated a high degree of adaptability to the consequences of sanctions and a critical reduction in commodity and energy imports from the West, successfully addressing issues related to the diversification of fuel and energy supplies to the Asia-Pacific region.

Summing up the research, it can be concluded that the imposition of sanctions has caused a systemic degradation of trade and economic relations with unfriendly countries, which has led to a reconfiguration of Russia's international economic cooperation. The large-scale pivot towards Asia and the Middle East has significantly increased the shares of China, India, and Turkey in Russia's trade turnover, thereby increasing the foreign trade risk associated with the concentration of the Russian Federation's commodity flows on a narrow group of neutral states.

Meanwhile, the development of international relations in distant markets of other neutral countries is disadvantageous for Russia due to existing logistical challenges.

Under pressure from Western countries, threats of secondary sanctions and trade restrictions are emerging, complicating the diversification of Russian assets.

Under these conditions, the state policy of the Russian Federation should be based on the development of international relations through the organization of full-scale cooperation with all interested countries. This entails the active participation of business representatives in accessible globalization, multilateral, and regional formats, continuing the course of openness towards free trade zones, and implementing political-diplomatic and commercial support for foreign and domestic projects of Russian business.

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